

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B432
 Date: 27 Feb 2009
 Take Off: 11:04:47Z 17:25:01Z
 Landing: 16:13:13Z 18:23:08Z
 Flight Time: 5h 08m 26s 0h 58m 07s

Campaign: APPRAISE – Wave Clouds

Operating Area: Highlands, Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Al Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	Y
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	Y
6	Core Chem	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM	N
7	Cloud Physics 1	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	Y
8	Cloud Physics 2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	N
9	Wet Nephelometer / PSAP	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	Y / N
10	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	N
11	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester University	N
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

The following log sheets are not available for this flight :

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Track plot	
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Wet Neph	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	30 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_112327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_122327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_132327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_142327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_152327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_162327_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_112316_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_122316_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_132316_1hz.avi
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 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_152322_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090227_r0_b432_162322_1hz.avi

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B432
 Date: 27 February 2009
 Project: APPRAISE - Wave cloud
 Location: Highlands, Scotland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
095109		Start-Up	0.17 kft	308	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
104418		ASP	0.16 kft	308	Open
110447		T/O	0.74 kft	308	Cranfield
112238		Video	24.0 kft	328	Start recording
120324	121916	Profile 1	23.4 - 5.2 kft	331	
121933	123202	Run 1	5.2 - 5.5 kft	076	QNH1005
123217	123254	Profile 2	5.5 - 6.0 kft	035	
123255	124649	Run 2	6.0 kft	306	
124704	124749	Profile 3	6.0 - 6.5 kft	243	
124750	125955	Run 3	6.5 kft	143	
125955	130057	Profile 4	6.5 - 7.0 kft	079	
130057	131623	Run 4	7.0 kft	304	
131624	131737	Profile 5	7.0 - 7.5 kft	264	
131737	133116	Run 5	7.5 kft	102	
132337		Event	7.5 kft	093	Heimann cal
133117	133240	Profile 6	7.5 - 8.0 kft	077	
133241	134920	Run 6	8.0 kft	250	
134921	135003	Profile 7	8.0 - 8.5 kft	265	
135003	140230	Run 7	8.5 kft	183	
140230	140508	Profile 8	8.5 - 11.0 kft	089	Relocate
140508	141446	Run 8	11.0 kft	014	Relocate
141447	141730	Profile 9	11.0 - 9.0 kft	014	
141730	142339	Run 9	9.0 kft	262	
142339	142519	Profile 10	9.0 - 10.5 kft	246	
142520	143230	Run 10	10.5 kft	071	
143231	143302	Profile 11	10.5 - 10.1 kft	091	
143302	144501	Run 11	10.1 - 10.0 kft	028	
144501	144603	Profile 12	10.0 - 9.5 kft	259	
144603	145357	Run 12	9.5 kft	122	
145357	145427	Profile 13	9.5 - 9.0 kft	089	
145437	150509	Run 13	9.0 kft	003	
150510	150625	Profile 14	9.0 - 9.5 kft	270	Move south
150625	151322	Run 14	9.5 kft	108	
151322	151626	Profile 15	9.5 - 8.0 kft	358	
151627	151845	Run 15	8.0 - 7.0 kft	281	
151708		Event	8.0 kft	271	Zero Nevz
151906	152530	Run 16	7.0 kft	258	
152530	152648	Profile 17	7.0 - 6.3 kft	267	to 6 kft,QNH1001
152648	153457	Run 17	6.3 - 6.4 kft	092	
153804	154608	Run 17.2	6.4 kft	271	6 kft
154903		Transit	12.6 kft	201	To Prestwick
161313		Land	0.01 kft	275	Prestwick
161726		ASP	0.00 kft	289	Close
161820		Shutdown	0.00 kft	289	55'30.43N, 4'35.93W
170637		Start-Up	0.01 kft	303	55'30.43N, 4'35.91W
171821		ASP	0.01 kft	050	Open
172501		T/O	1.3 kft	303	Prestwick
172932		Event	9.9 kft	136	Zero JW & Nevz
180300	181152	Run 18	10.0 - 9.9 kft	099	WAS sampling,bottle 34-37
182308		Land	0.22 kft	222	Cranfield
182512		ASP	0.21 kft	356	Close
182900		Shutdown	0.21 kft	306	52'04.38N, 0'37.48W

Sortie Brief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies

Date: 27 Feb 2009

B432: t/o 10:30z Cranfield, land & refuel (Prestwick) ~ 16:00z; t/o ~17:00z, land 18:15z

M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in **wave clouds** and their interaction with local aerosol.

Sortie Location: Areas Bravo and Charlie. In layers of wave cloud over south western Scotland to the east of first range of mountains

Sortie Summary: Flights through orographic wave clouds will be used to study possible changes in the microphysics of the clouds that form further downwind as a result of their formation on aerosols and trace gasses that were modified by their previous interaction with wave clouds further upwind. Hence the flight is designed to measure changes to both cloud and aerosol properties following their interaction in earlier waves. Initially a profile will be flown up wind of the cloud to assess the vertical structure of the atmosphere with respect to trace gases and aerosol properties. Straight and level runs will then be made along the wind, above within and below the wave clouds. These runs will cover the full horizontal extent of the cloud (along wind) and will be an investigation of both the microphysical evolution of the cloud and the influence of the cloud on the aerosol properties. These will be supplemented by runs upstream, within and downstream of individual wave clouds perpendicular to the mean wind so as to investigate in greater detail the effects of the cloud processing on the aerosol properties, and the differences between cloud properties in subsequent waves.

Sortie Detail :

- a. T+0 Take off and climb to FL200 for transit to operating area
 - b. T+70 Perform vertical profile through wave clouds from below cloud base (if possible) to aircraft ceiling, or to above wave cloud top (whichever is lower).
 - c. T+90 Descend to below wave cloud bases and perform straight and level run along the mean wind direction 300 feet below cloud base for n* number of wave clouds.
 - d. T+100 Turn through 180 degrees. Ascend to cloud base and perform straight and level run through cloud bases (ie in cloud).
 - e. T+110 Turn through 180 degrees, ascend to middle of wave cloud and perform straight and level run along wind for n* waves.
 - f. T+120 Turn through 180 degrees, ascend to return to upwind edge of the cloud in an above cloud run (along mean wind)
 - g. T+130 Perform straight and level run in inflow to cloud, across wind, ahead of the cloud edge for full width of the cloud.
 - h. T+140 Travel downwind to middle of the cloud and make straight and level run in-cloud (across wind) for the width of the cloud
 - i. T+150 Travel to downwind edge of the cloud and make straight and level run out of cloud across wind for the width of the cloud
 - j. T+160 repeat the sequence g-i (as time permits) to measure the inflow, incloud properties and outflow of subsequent wave clouds (NB stage i of a previous wave maybe the same SLR as stage g for the next wave depending on spacing of waves).
 - k. T+320 land and refuel
 - l. T+380 takeoff for return transit
 - m. T+430 land Cranfield
- (* number of waves "n" will need to be determined insitu)

PROJECT BRIEF: APPRAISE-Clouds – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems, altocumulus clouds, wave clouds and cumulus clouds within the temperature regime in which ice particles will likely co-exist with liquid (typically 0 to -30C).

The flight plans are designed to characterise the aerosol above and below the cloud and infer aerosol fluxes into the cloud layer by combination with the vertical wind measurements and the microphysical characteristics within the cloud layer.

Constant altitude flight legs of approximately 50 km (10 minutes flying) will be made:

- In the boundary layer to measure the aerosol size distributions (from 10 nm to 100 um), CCN, aerosol composition from 30 nm to 1 um using the ToF AMS; larger particles and non-volatile material such as refractory material will be measured using EDAX analysis of filter samples.
- Near cloud base within cloud to measure the cloud droplets that have been activated from CCN, interstitial particles and larger particles that have fallen from cloud top. In addition the onset of ice will be observed using the CPI, CAPS and 2-D probes in cloud.
- Middle of the cloud passes will be made at temperatures where key processes will be expected to be initiated (-6C to -9C) for the Hallett-Mossop process or around -15C where fragmentation of dendritic crystals may be important.
- Near cloud top and within the cloud to measure entrainment and aerosols within entrained eddies and ice particles within the cloud; in colder clouds ice initiation will occur in this region.
- Above the cloud to measure the properties of aerosol particles that can potentially be entrained into the clouds.

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the CAMRa radar and lidar facilities at Chilbolton, Hants.

Weather conditions: Stratiform, or altocumulus clouds lying over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility, or wave clouds over Scotland. These may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. For Chilbolton flights it is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees allowing the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst almost parallel to the mean wind direction.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer, CR2
- GPS, GIN, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud/Aerosol Physics/Chemistry

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- 2DS, CAPS and FSSP – as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.
- AMS, SMPS/WCPC (- to sample off both Rosemount and CVI inlets*)
- Filters

*CVI (if fitted): for residuals (and Ly α) incloud; aerosols out of cloud (PCASP, CPC)

Mission Scientist Debrief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies:
Flight Numbers: B432, 27th Feb 2009 (Take-off 11:04z, landing 16:13z Prestwick),
B432b, recovery to Cranfield (Take-off 17:25z, landing 18:23z)
Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims & operating area: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in **wave clouds** and their interaction with local aerosol.

Weather conditions: For a number of days leading up to Feb 27th, conditions in the generally westerly flow had been suitable over the northern UK to set up wave clouds over Scotland and Northern England. These were observed to be present on each day since Saturday 21st (except Tuesday 24th), and so in the absence of frontal systems passing over southern England it was decided to investigate the evolution of the microphysical properties of these wave clouds and their interaction with precursor aerosol and gas species. For the 27th, the aviation forecaster at Exeter provided information from the 3D-FOM (flow over mountains) model (and by the Schutz method) that there was a good chance of wave activity over the northern UK. Vertical velocities of 700-800ft/min were forecasted at peak heights of 8-10kft for northern England, and although less over Scotland (~500ft/min) it was decided to work in this area because of difficulties in operating over northern England. The forecaster suggested the strongest activity would be in the morning leading up to midday, the activity easing down in the afternoon although waves would persist throughout the day. Based on this information a Cranfield takeoff time of 11:00z was set, with a refuelling stop at Prestwick around 16:00z before recovering to Cranfield.

Figure 1 shows the synoptic chart for midday on Feb 27th. It can be seen that a low pressure area exists out to the west of Iceland, with a high pressure centred over the Brest peninsula dominating the weather over southern England. A weak depression approaching Scotland from the west has generated a couple of warm fronts which at this time lie over the extreme NE of Scotland. Behind these the flow is generally westerly in the warm sector, ahead of the arrival of a cold front out to the west of Ireland. This situation led to the generation of wave clouds over Scotland and Northern England as forecasted. Figures 2 and 3 below show visible satellite images for the northern UK at 12:00z and 16:00z respectively (the approximate start and end times of science over Scotland during flight B432)

Figures 2 and 3: High resolution visible satellite images for the northern UK at 12:00z (left) and 16:00z (right) respectively on February 27th 2009

Summary of the flight: Following take-off, the aircraft ascended to FL240 to transit up to Scotland. At this level (392mbar, -33.4°C) the aircraft was just into the base of upper level cloud as it transited over the northwest midlands area approaching Manchester. Manchester cloud probes observed some small irregular ice crystals, some hexagonal plates, some bullet rosettes and aggregates of the latter. 2DC also saw some rosettes. Below there was a solid deck of low level cloud. Much further north over Scotland, “hummocks” could be seen in the tops of the lower cloud deck. At 56°N a profile descent P1, was started as the aircraft turned to head towards the west coast of Argyll. Cloud top (CT) was encountered at around 6kft (804mb, 1.82°C), and the profile was terminated following a left turn to head back east on a SLR (R1) at 5.2kft (835mar, -0.34°C), the MSA for the general terrain immediately inland. The leg was in and out of cloud as the plane passed through the crests and troughs of the waves (which ran N-S). After 5minutes the plane was gently eased up 200ft because of the rising terrain, completing the rest of R1 at 5.5kft (826mbar, 1.6°C). After a turn and a short profile ascent P2 to 6kft (811mb, m2.23°C) to head back west, a series of SLRs (R2-R7) were carried out E-W and W-E (perpendicular the crests and troughs of the waves) at ascending altitudes, spaced at 500ft intervals up to the 8.5kft level. Across individual runs, temperatures

varied by around 1.5-2.0°C and correlated with vertical velocity, the colder sections often coinciding with in-cloud periods. Similar trends in O₃ and aerosol concentrations were observed, as well as in CO (but to a lesser extent). The CT altitudes varied with location (N-S as well as W-E), as did the microphysical properties of the cloud (such as cloud water content – see Figures 4-9 below). After R4 at 7kft (781mbar, T varying between 0.35°C out of cloud to ~ -2.8°C in-cloud across the run) there was little cloud at subsequent levels, although in certain regions small lenticular capping clouds formed above the crest of the wave clouds below, and an attempt was made to fly through these on some runs. The final SLR R7 (W-E) in this series at 8.5kft (738mbar) was entirely above cloud for the full duration

Figures 4-9: Johnson-Williams and Nevzorov liquid and total water contents for Runs 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 (left to right and top to bottom) at 5.5, 6.0, 6.5, 7.0, 7.5, and 8.0kft (826, 811, 790, 781, 766 and 751mbar) respectively (on alternating W-E and E-W reciprocal headings)

Visible satellite pictures (12UTC and later) suggested the wave clouds further to the NE may not be embedded within a full deck of low level cloud, and furthermore being over higher terrain may have been colder and therefore more likely glaciated. The decision was taken to move to this area (to say 57.4°N, 3.25°W) so following R7 a W-E run, a profile ascent (P8) up to 11kft (669mbar, -5.8°C) was carried out and a transit (R8) to the new area undertaken. Following a turn to return E-W, a profile descent (P9) to 9kft was carried out. During the turn in cloud, core cloud saw columns and CPI saw columns, needles and plates. R9 westbound at 9kft (723mbar, -4.23°C) encountered cloud regions, but again these were mainly liquid (although aircraft anti-icing detected icing). A profile

ascent up to 10.5kft was carried out to return eastbound, in an attempt to sample the mixed phase cloud seen in the initial turn at the eastern extreme of the transit to the NE, however cloud was not encountered until the end of R10 (682mbar, -7.2°C). Again ice cloud was encountered in the turn and descent to 10kft for the reciprocal SLR E-W, R11 (695mbar, -6.7°C), the turbulence probe iced up and icing was observed on the pylons. However, soon after the start of R11 the aircraft emerged into cloud free air for the remainder of the run. As before in the west, lenticular clouds were present above wave crests, and attempts were made to fly through some of these, but without great success. By this time the tops of the cloud within wave crests were descending rapidly and the cloud deck below was thinning and breaking up. Despite a number of attempts to descend and fly SLRs through these thinning clouds success was limited, and by R17 eastbound and R17.2 westbound the MSA of 6000ft for this elevated area (6.3kft on 1001mb p setting) was reached and no further descent was possible. Shortly after this the aircraft was flown back to the western coast for refuelling at Prestwick, before carrying out a relocation flight back south to Cranfield.

Figure 10: Flight track showing first series of SLR legs over Argyll to the west, and also showing second series of runs further to the NE in an attempt to find non-embedded wave clouds

Notes on instrumentation:

All the major instruments worked fine throughout. The turbulence probe iced up at one point in the second series of SLRs out in the NE region. F-FSSP lost around 10minutes of data at one point, and CIP100 showed negative diameters for a similar period – but this was at a time when there was little to measure. There was a CO alarm on descent into Prestwick. See flight folder for a full summary of instrument status.

Mission Scientist's Log (ADPRAISE-CLOUDS)

Flight No B...432 Date 27/02/09 Name KN BOWER Page 1 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					+1°C, 230/10kts
10:36:59	(KNB)	10:39:20			Engine Start 4-1
10:40:00	"				Power Change Over
10:44:20	"				T _{tot} 1019 mb 310 ft
10:48:05					Hold - ATC
11:01:18					T _{tot} 230/11kts
11:05:14					Rolling
11:05:41					T ₁₀
		2700			CB (P → 1013 mb)
		3380			CT.
11.11.30	≡	11.12:20	KNB	(+50 _s)	Turn Check
11.13.24	Ascent	FL150	308	52°0'/0°36'	572mb -11.42°/-16.44°C <u>157m/s/307°</u> ?
11.16.56	Ascent	FL200	305	52°0'/0°36'	466mb -22.51°/-33.26°C <u>108m/s/307°</u> ?
12.21.06	Transit	FL240	330	53°0'/1°36'	Just into CB:- CPI 392mb -33.37°/-34.68° 21/10'
					Voron - small inregs some - heac plates + some eggs' bullette rosettes
					All B.R, made 150µm new (CPI)
11.29.01	Transit	FL240	328	53°36'/2°6'	Core cloud sees B.R. - but hard to tell...
11.31.30	Transit	FL240			Xtals - less organized new + hint of liquid.
11.58.16	Transit	FL240	333	55°48'/3°54'	392mb -34.2°/-39.75°C 33m/s/259°
12.03.24	PI start	FL290	331	56°12'/4°6'	Can see schil deep below - with hummocks
12.06.17	PI	20.4kft	270	56°24'/4°18'	456mb, -26.47°/32.32°C 27m/s/260°
12.08.43	PI	17.9kft	254	56°24'/4°36'	506mb, -19.63°/-37.34°C 22m/s/254°
12.15.10	PI	9.9kft	255	56°15'/5°18'	697mb, -4.43°/-6.34°C 18m/s/243°

(IN)
(IN)

(192.168.101.145. VNC)

[1005, 1003, 1002]
Bulfol, Patree,

Cloud Top ~ 6000ft

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...432 Date 27/02/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 2 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12.19.13	P1 end	5.2kft	96°	56°12'/5°30'	834mb, -0.71°/-1.0°C, 4m/s/217°
12.19.27	R1 start	5.3kft	77°	56°12'/5°30'	835mb, -0.34°/5.07°C, 4m/s/224°
					In and out of cloud.
12.29.30	R1 1	5.3kft	74°	56°18'/4°54'	Easing Up to 5200' for terrain clearance.
12.32.01	R1 end	5.5kft	71°	56°24'/4°00'	826mb, 1.64°/2.99°C 14m/s/277°
12.32.14	P2	5.5kft	27°	56°24'/4°00'	826mb, 1.41°/2.5°C 14m/s/274°
12.32.53	P2E/R2	6.0kft	313°	56°24'/4°00'	811mb, 2.23°C/1.32°C 18m/s/264°
12.42.36	R2	6.0kft	265°	56°18'/4°54'	811mb, -0.69°/-1.4°C 12m/s/248°
12.46.47	R2E/P3St	6kft	266°	56°18'/5°24'	811mb, -2.13°C/-0.91°C 7m/s/227°
12.47.46	P3E/R3St	6.5kft	150	56°18'/5°24'	796mb, -0.84°/-2.52°C 9m/s/258°
12.52.17	R3	6.5kft	77°	56°18'/4°54'	Into cloud here. 795mb -0.44°/16.35° 10m/s/264°
					higher tentacle clouds above-base cloud to N
					so will move N-'climb and do parallel
					track to this next -----
12.59.55	R3E/R4S	6.5kft	79°	56°24'/3°54'	796mb, -0.91°/0.05°C 12m/s/270°
13.00.55	P4E/R4S	7.0kft	309°	56°30'/3°54'	781mb, -0.2°C/1.53°C 16m/s/275°
					O ₃ - features 5-10 mb changes
					(will drift to N to catch cloud)
					CO - not so much
					Aerosol is Organic dominated
13.04.15	R4	7.0kft	269°	56°24'/4°12'	Out of cloud. 78mb, 0.35°/0.58°C 18m/s/252°
13.06.17	R4	7.0kft	267°	56°24'/4°24'	In cloud. 781mb -1.33°/-1.14°C 14m/s/257°
13.06.53	R4	7.0kft	267°	56°24'/4°24'	Out cloud 780mb 0.06°/-5.87°C 19m/s/244°
13.08.36	R4	7.0kft	265°	56°24'/4°36'	In cloud 781mb -2.81°/-2.18°C 13m/s/255°
13.09.05	R4	7.0kft	269°	56°24'/4°42'	Out cloud 781mb -2.86°/-19.8°C 12m/s/255°
13.09.50	R4	7.0kft	270°	56°24'/4°42'	In cloud 782mb -2.23°/-11.99°C 13m/s/256°

364

(go to ~ 57.4 N°)
(just miss??) 325 W

probe with CRP
17mm

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.432 Date 27/02/08 Name K.N. Bower Page 3 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13.10.59	R4	7.0kft	268	56°24'4"54'	0kt 761mb -2.61/-3.42°C 13m/s/243°
					Aerial Mass and Veloc Velocit correlation too
13.14.49	R4	7.0kft	268	56°24'5"18'	0km, bumpy cloud 761mb 2.22/-27.7° 17/239°
13.16.22	R4E/P55	7.0kft	267	56°24'5"24'	761mb, 1.42/-25.5°C 16m/s/246°
13.17.35	P5E/P5	7.5kft	109	56°24'5"24'	766mb, 0.86/-32.93°C 14m/s/237°
13.22.45	P5	7.5kft	94	56°24'4"48'	just into CT, bumpy in turn 766mb -2.06/-17.15° 12m/s/252°
13.31.14	P5E/P65	7.5kft	84	56°24'3"36'	766mb, -0.36/-1.1°C 14m/s/267°
13.32.37	P6E/P6	8.0kft	255	56°30'3"36'	761mb, -1.11°C/-2.75° 19m/s/250°
13.33.57	R6	8.0kft	224	56°24'3"42'	761mb -1.94/-1.58 15m/s/256°
13.38.41	R6	8.0kft	270	56°24'4"12'	Under Sep lenticular cloud -1.85/-7.27°C
13.39.34	R6	8.0kft	269	56°24'4"18'	762mb, -0.1/-4.9°C 17m/s/242°
13.49.18	R6E/P75	8.0kft	265	56°24'5"18'	762mb 0.27/-23.1°C 14m/s/231°
13.50.02	P7E/P75	8.5kft	190	56°24'5"24'	736mb -0.55°C/-34.93° 16m/s/230°
13.53.43	R7	8.5kft	95	56°24'4"54'	737mb -1.1°C/-23.82°C 14m/s/253°
14.02.29	R7E/P85	8.5kft	94	56°24'3"48'	737mb -1.31/-7.47°C 13m/s/259°
14.05.10	P8E/R8	11.0kft	14	56°36'3"36'	669mb -5.81/-17.53°C 16m/s/263°
14.09.31	R8	11.0kft	12	56°54'3"24'	669mb -5.36/-17.62° 20m/s/274°
14.14.46	R8E/P9	11.0kft	14	57°12'3"6'	669mb -5.13°C/-27.92°C 20m/s/271°
14.17.24	P9E/P9	9.0kft	262	57°18'3"18'	723mb -4.32°C/-3.35°C 16m/s/262°
					save column - by Core Cloud - CPJ, (Columns, Needles & Plates)
14.19.42	R9	9.0kft	262	57°18'3"36'	723mb -3.25/-3.9°C 16m/s/259°
14.21.53	R9	9.0kft	250	57°12'3"48'	723mb -3.41/-3.51°C 16m/s/251°
14.23.40	R9E/P105	9.0kft	246	57°12'4"0'	723mb -1.67/14.46°C 18m/s/259°
14.25.19	P10E/R10	10.5kft	71	57°6'3"54'	682mb -5.09/-32.61°C 17m/s/277°

(Turn into Cloud & descend)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 432 Date 27/02/09 Name K. N. BOWER Page 4 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
14.31.28	R10	10.5kft	93	57°12'3"0"	alc anti ice - CPI all H ₂ O (R) -7.17°/10.93°
14.32.29	R10E/R11	10.5kft	92	57°6'2"48"	681mb, -7.2°/-12.72° at 15m/s/281°
14.32.59	R11E/R11	10.0kft	34	57°12'2"48"	into ice cloud in turn - columnar - con cloud
					-also CPI sees them -6.69°C/-7.22°C,
					* lost Turbulence probe 16m/s/285°C
					"icing on the pylons" - CPI
14.36.46	R11	10.0kft	274	57°12'3"6"	Out of cloud now; 695mb -5.6/-7.59 — heading for a lenticular cloud ahead
14.40.49	R11	10kft	274	57°12'3"30"	Just over lenticular... 695mb -5.01/-4.15° — (not quite low enough)
14.44.50	R11E/PR3	10.0kft	271	57°12'3"54"	695mb, -3.54/-36.7° - turb probe still used up.
14.46.03	R12E/R12	9.5kft	122	57°6'3"54"	711mb -1.81/-31.89° "
					CPC ~ 300 cm ⁻³ }
					PCASD - 14 cm ⁻³ }
					CAS - < 1 cm ⁻³ }
14.52.59	R12	9.5kft	91	57°12'3"0"	709mb, -4.62°/-4.1°C (30m/s/186°)
14.54.04	R12E/PR3	9.4kft	79	57°12'2"54"	710mb, -2.75°/-14.76° "(16m/s/206°)"
14.54.27	R13E/R13	9.0kft	24	57°12'2"45"	723mb, -3.94°C/-0.41°C (3m/s/73°)
14.54.59	R13	9.0kft	312	57°12'3"65"	alc anti ice 722mb -4.22°C/-3.85°C — small on 2DC
					COP - 14,000 cm ⁻³ 25 μ
					PS50 - ~ 75 cm ⁻³ 15 μ
14.55.06	R13E/PR3	9.0kft	271	57°12'3"48"	723mb, -1.43°/-13.62° almost got turbulence probe back.
15.06.23	R13E/R13	9.4kft	114	57°6'3"48"	710mb, -1.59°/-30.86° — offset to South 4 miles to try to intercept lenticular clouds

turb mba

[can see clouds breaking up below - not sure we have wave clouds] * turb probe back *

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...432 Date 27/02/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 5 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
15.13.21	R14E/P15	9.5kft	358	57°6'/2°54'	709mb, -2.64°/-30.51°C, 17/277°
15.15.09	P15	9.0kft	248	57°6'/3°6'	723mb -3.25°/-11.94°C 15m/s/267°
15.15.09	P15	8.5kft			723 (missed screen down)
15.16.29	R15E/R15	8.0kft	281	57°6'/3°12'	731mb, -1.09°/-9.29°C
15.17.42	R15E/P16	8.0kft	272	57°6'/3°24'	752mb, 0.24°/-8.62°C 16m/s/261°
15.18.41	P16E/R16	7.0kft	254	57°6'/3°24'	780mb 0.21°/-6.81°C 16m/s/248°
15.22.28	R16	7.0kft	268	57°6'/3°44'	Cloud tops 761mb -1.65°/-19.64°C 14m/s/236°
15.25.28	R16E/P17	7.0kft	269	57°6'/4°6'	780mb, 0.22°/25.8°C 17m/s/245°
15.26.40	P17E/R17	6.3kft	113	57°0'/4°12'	(am: 1001mb pxtkn) 6000ft Altimeter
		Minus.			801mb -0.63°C/-19.74°C 9m/s/237°
15.30.52	R17	6.3kft	91	57°6'/3°42'	Into cloud now 800mb -3.05°/-15.01° 9m/s/254°
15.31.33	R17	6.3kft	93	57°6'/3°36'	Out of cloud now 802mb 3.35°/+0.5°C 15/255°
15.34.56	R17E	6.3kft	90	57°6'/3°6'	6000ft Altimeter 2.86°/-19.61° 12m/s/263°
15.36.04	R17.2SE	6.3kft	271	57°0'/3°18'	6000ft/800mb 1.62°/-13.67° 16m/s/243.
15.39.37	R17.2	6.3kft	270	57°0'/3°24'	CT's - into here 801mb/6000' -0.69°/9.21° 13/234°
17.40.15	R17.2	6.3kft	268	57°0'/3°30'	Out of cloud now -0.41°/-3.22°C 15m/s/286°
15.41.38	R17.2	6.3kft	267	57°0'/3°36'	CT's again 1.22°/-21.14°C 14m/s/232°
15.42.08	R17.2	6.3kft	267	57°0'/3°42'	Out of cloud 0.23°/+0.09°C 17m/s/233°
15.44.15	R17.2	6.3kft	265	57°0'/3°54'	In cloud again -1.96°/-8.63°C 10m/s/211°
15.44.27	R17.2	6.3kft	265	57°0'/3°54'	Out of cloud -1.54°/-1.11°C 13m/s/219°
15.46.12	R17.2E	6.3kft	271	57°0'/4°6'	799mb +1.03°/-37.9°C 16m/s/239°
					1014 250/10kts
16.13.59	KND				landing
					end taxi
16.17.53					Power Changeover.

(1001mb, 1004mb)
(Portner, Oortman)

Mission Scientist's Log (APPRAISE-CLOUDS-recorng)

Flight No B 432B Date 27/02/01 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 1 of 1

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					(QNM 1014)
17.14.04	(KNS) -	17.15.57			Engine Skid (4-1)
17.16.52	"				Power change over
17.17.58	"				Taxi
17.19.49	"				Hold
17.20.30	"				Taxi
17.25.20	"				Rolling (230/3kts)
17.25.49	"				T/O
		4450'			CB
		5720'			CT.
17.28.30		6000'			Clear (Cloud free).
17.44.00	HOVER#	17:49.50	KNS		Time Check.
17.33.42		FL152			
17.43.04		FL250			
18.02.41		FL100			Start of Run for WAS bottles
18.23.56					Landing

260°/6kts W°C/6°

B432 Xchat log

*** 1 FAAM_GLUXE (~vircuser@203.52.191.254)1 has joined #APPCLOUDS
[1 FAAM_GLUXE1] testing
<1 FAAMOpsDetach1 > Reading you this end Mo
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Doug back at the helm Dave T bag in my oot
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Boot!
*** 1 DFL_Ops (~vircuser@host86-153-16-34.range86-153.btcentralplus.com)1 has joined #APPCLOUDS
[1 FAAM_GLUXE1] Currently in Wave cloud, but it's all warm. Phil R
<1 DFL_Ops1 > ERE
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Avalon confirm 'once in lifetime' offer extended to Monday for AMS!
[1 FAAM_GLUXE1] does that mean they have power to aircraft over weekend?
*** Server connection lost
*** Server connection lost
*** 1 FAAM_GLUXE (~vircuser@203.52.191.254)1 has joined #APPCLOUDS
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > confirm AMS power all w/e as per last night
[1 FAAM_GLUXE1] Keith Says thank-you ver much, please pass thanks on to avalon
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Can Mo tell me where the paperwork the BBC sent here has gone. They waht a copy of it sent back for some reason. Passed thanks already to Avalon
[1 FAAM_GLUXE1] Mo says try bill Tobin or Mike Collins. They have been deeling with bbc.
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Hannah said she had sent something to Mo. Did she not rx anything? Have the details for DFL to resnd what they faxed.
[1 FAAM_GLUXE1] Mo has rx nothing unless during flying today. what does your last sentence mean? It doesn't make sense to me.
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Checked again and finally got correct story. It was DFL stuff they wanted and will get via scan in email now.
[1 FAAM_GLUXE1] okay
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Is ur eta Cran 1845? Dave T can catch a train at Slough at 20:35, arr. Ext St Davids @ 2306
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Alt trainline Woking 2046 arr Ext 2354
*** 1 DFL_Ops (~vircuser@host86-153-16-34.range86-153.btcentralplus.com)1 has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 240 seconds]
*** 1 DFL_Ops (~vircuser@host86-153-16-34.range86-153.btcentralplus.com)1 has joined #APPCLOUDS
[1 FAAM_GLUXE1] eta approx 18:30, how's dave going to get to woking?
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > I can drop Dave at Slough or Woking depending on traffic
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Monday is APPRAISE or nothing now. Not sure you were online 4 that message
*** 1 FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@host86-153-16-34.range86-153.btcentralplus.com)1 has quit IRC [Quit: User pushed the X - because it's Xtra, baby]
*** 1 Avalon (~vircuser@host86-143-241-144.range86-143.btcentralplus.com)1 has joined #APPCLOUDS
<1 Avalon1 > Avalon now online
[1 FAAM_GLUXE1] eta prestwick 16:20
<1 DFL_Ops1 > flt plan filed for 1710 dep fl230 high speed cruise
*** Server connection lost
*** Server connection lost
*** Server connection lost
*** Nickname is already in use: 1 FAAM_GLUXE1
*** 1 FAAM_MSci (~vircuser@203.38.13.8)1 has joined #APPCLOUDS
*** 1 FAAM_GLUXE (~vircuser@203.52.191.254)1 has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 240 seconds]
*** 1 DFL_Ops (~vircuser@host86-153-16-34.range86-153.btcentralplus.com)1 has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 240 seconds]
*** 1 DFL_Ops (~vircuser@host86-153-16-34.range86-153.btcentralplus.com)1 has joined #APPCLOUDS
*** 1 DFL_Ops (~vircuser@host86-153-16-34.range86-153.btcentralplus.com)1 has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 240 seconds]
*** 1 DFL_Ops (~vircuser@host86-153-16-34.range86-153.btcentralplus.com)1 has joined #APPCLOUDS
<1 DFL_Ops1 > are you on your way yet ???
[1 FAAM_MSci1] Just taken off
[1 FAAM_MSci1] eta cranfield 18:25
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Can Keith confirm Manchester APPRAISE crew for next week?
[1 FAAM_MSci1] He says he needs to be on the ground to sort it
[1 FAAM_MSci1] Seems he does not need to be on the ground. Same crew next week
[1 FAAM_MSci1] :)
*** 1 DFL_Ops (~vircuser@host86-153-16-34.range86-153.btcentralplus.com)1 has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 240 seconds]
<1 FAAMOpsDoug1 > Thanks

Cloud Physics Flight Log B432

Date:27/02/09	Operator:PR	DRS Time:yes	DAU1 Time:yes	DAU2 Time:also yes	DAU3 Time:no	AUX1 Time:maybe	Aux2 Time:?
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	PCASP		2DC		2DP		CDP		FFSSP		UMan FSSP		PIP	
Operated?	Y		Y		No Chance		Y		Y		Y		y	
Pre-flight checks	Vref (>7):		EI#1 V (>1):	-2.1	EI#1V:		Laser V(~3):	4.1	Ref V (~3):	3.0	Laser V (~9):		EI#1 V:	
	Flow (~1):	0.78	EI#32 V (>1):	-2.1									EI #1V:	
	Pressure:	1007											EI#64 V:	
	Temp (NDIT)	12.5												

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size		Blocks Tx	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	Counts	Max size	LWC	
11:05																	All heater on OK
12:03:25	Fl240	4	0.07	0	0			74									P1
13:04:25	Fl 230	6	0.07														
12:05:09	22	9	0.07														
12:06:46	20	6	0.07														
12:07:43	19	3	0.07														
12:08:40	18	10	0.07														
12:09:40	17	11	0.07														
12:10:29	16	41	0.07														
12:11:12	15	33	0.07														
12:12:01	14	15	0.07														
12:12:50	13	14	0.07														
12:13:33	12	15	0.07														
12:24:27	11	25	0.07														
12:15:12	10	20	0.07														
12:16:04	9	35	0.07														
12:16:51	8	45	0.07														
12:17:48	7	72	0.07														
	6			14													
12:19:18	5	81	0.07	14	125			1	138	100	22.5	75	20	0.016	600		Run 1
12:23:18	5	26	0.06														
12:27:00	5	400	0.14	400	100			1	312	40	35	50	20	0.035	100		
12:31:00		300	0.07	500	175			1	404	30	25	25	20	0	0		
12:32:57	6	10	0.08														Run 2

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	Counts	Max size	LWC	
13:36:00	6	300	0.2	400	175			1	517	30	35	20	25	?	?	?	
13:40:00	6	170	0.2	3000	225			1	657	20	45	25	20				
13:44:00	6	33	0.07														
12:47:48	7	71	0.06														Run 3
12:55:00	6.5	55	0.06														
12:59:00	6.5	60	0.21	915	125			1	896	20	40	40	201				
13:00:57	7	50		20	75			1	958	80	20	100	15				Run 4
13:04																	CIP log froze, probe and logging restarted Measuring - MVD
13:08:00	7	500	0.19	240	150			1	1151	20	35	50	10				
13:12:00	7	30	0.07														
13:17:40	7.5	107	0.07														Run 5
13:32:40	8	4	0.17	0	0			1	1256	100	15	100	10				Run 6
13:36:00	8	27	0.07														
13:50:04	8.5	22	0.07														Run 7
14:05:09	11	15	0.08														
14:14:47		40	0.18	126	150			columns	1327	30	35	17	15				
14:17:28	9	16	0.26	45	125			1	1355	30	27	13	15				Run 8
14:21:55	9	215	0.22	600	175			1	1361	60	30	75	30				
14:25:21	10.5	15	0.07														Run 10
14:31:40	10.5	20	0.11	38	75			1	1361	80	25	100	15				
14:33:05		109	0.25	250	450			Ice/1	1361								FFSSP froze, restarted
14:37:00	10	21	0.07														
14:42:33	10	32	0.07														
14:53:00		5	0.27					1	42	100	30						
14:54:47	9	35	0.28	140	275			1	66	40	30	30	20				
15:30:54	6.3	188	0.2	10	100			1	131	60	25	50	20				
FLIGHT	BACK	TO	CRAN	Field													
	Pcasp	Flow	0.84														
	Press		1012														
	temp		9.74														

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B432

Date: 27/02/09

Instruments

1. Rosemount DI heater found to be not heating on pre-flight. Changed housing then okay. Transferred original element to new housing.
2. GIN – Okay on switch on but froze position after t/o. Red SYS led on. Recycled power but SYS led still came up red. Recycled again, left it off for 15 seconds, then okay.
3. CPS – Reset pressure to 500mb after t/o
4. Radalt – Reading 0 at 5kft. Recycled PAFT CB then okay
5. CIP 100 – reading particles with –ve diameter. Tried recycling power. Okay after 10 minutes.
6. Turb Probe – Iced over 1436Z - AOSS diff and check & AOA diff paras affected. Back online at 1507Z
7. FFC camera window froze over on initial profile into operating area, 1205Z. Cleared at 1512Z
8. Headset No 6 – starting to come apart at one of the earpiece hinges
9. CO – red alarm led on during approach to Prestwick. Cleared itself. Data okay on HORACE

General Status from debrief]

Dry/Wet Nephs and PSAP – all okay

Core Cloud – FFSSP lost data for 10 minutes, then okay

AMS – Reduced sensitivity (after B432) but otherwise okay

-

Issues

Flight:

B432

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B432

Date: 27/02/09

Instruments

1. Rosemount DI heater found to be not heating on pre-flight. Changed housing then okay.
Transferred original element to new housing.
2. GIN – Okay on switch on but froze position after t/o. Red SYS led on. Recycled power but SYS led still came up red. Recycled again, left it off for 15 seconds, then okay.
3. CPS – Reset pressure to 500mb after t/o
4. Radalt – Reading 0 at 5kft. Recycled PAFT CB then okay
5. CIP 100 – reading particles with –ve diameter. Tried recycling power. Okay after 10 minutes.
6. Turb Probe – Iced over 1436Z - AOSS diff and check & AOA diff paras affected. Back online at 1507Z
7. FFC camera window froze over on initial profile into operating area, 1205Z. Cleared at 1512Z
8. Headset No 6 – starting to come apart at one of the earpiece hinges
9. CO – red alarm led on during approach to Prestwick. Cleared itself. Data okay on HORACE

General Status from debrief]

Dry/Wet Nephs and PSAP – all okay

Core Cloud – FFSSP lost data for 10 minutes, then okay

AMS – Reduced sensitivity (after B432) but otherwise okay

-

Issues

Flow A

Flow B

Temperature A

Temperature B

Numb Conc

DMT

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 27 Feb 2009 1100 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 27 Feb 2009 1200 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 27 Feb 2009 1200 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 27 Feb 2009 1300 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 27 Feb 2009 1300 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 27 Feb 2009 1400 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 27 Feb 2009 1400 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 27 Feb 2009 1500 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 27 Feb 2009 1500 UTC

FL150 in climb to FL220

No GIN ??

FL240 - just into cloud

CPI see bullet rosettes 150um passing Pol

New plot, same times

Flight B432 11:32:54
Heading 327 deg Speed 332 knots Height 24.0kft Press 392mb
Lat 53°54.0'N Long 2°18.0'W Wind 23 ms-1/ 281 deg
Temp -34.22C Dewpoint -33.61C
From 11:05:00 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 41574 secs
CO MIXING RATIO 98.76 ppb

All sc

New plot, same times

Flight B432 11:33:47
Heading 328 deg Speed 335 knots Height 24.0kft Press 392mb
Lat 54°0.0'N Long 2°24.0'W Wind 23 ms-1/ 280 deg
Temp -34.15C Dewpoint -32.86C
From 11:05:00 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 41625 secs
OZONE MIXING RATIO 18.65 ppb

All sc

Wave cloud below

Solid deck below, contrails above + shadows below

Zero cal on Nev

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Start P1

Flight B432 12:05:29

Heading 331 deg Speed 281 knots Height 21.5kft Press 435mb

Lat 56°24.0'N Long 4°12.0'W Wind 29 ms-1/260 deg

Temp -28.02C Dewpoint -36.9C

From 11:05:00 to now

Current values
 ++++ STATIC PRESSURE 435.87 mb
 ++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -28.02 deg C
 ++++ DEW POINT -36.9 deg C

Flight B432 12:06:17

Heading 270 deg Speed 261 knots Height 20.4kft Press 456mb

Lat 56°24.0'N Long 4°18.0'W Wind 27 ms-1/260 deg

Temp -26.47C Dewpoint -32.32C

From 11:05:00 to now

Current values
 — GIN LONGITUDE -4.34 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
 — GIN LATITUDE 56.46 deg (+ve N)

Flight B432 12:08:43
Heading 254 deg Speed 296 knots Height 17.9kft Press 506mb
Lat 56°24.0'N Long 4°36.0'W Wind 22 ms-1/ 254 deg
Temp -19.63C Dewpoint -37.74C
From 11:05:00 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -4.61 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 56.42 deg (+ve N)

Flight B432 12:15:10
Heading 255 deg Speed 234 knots Height 9.9kft Press 697mb
Lat 56°18.0'N Long 5°18.0'W Wind 18 ms-1/ 243 deg
Temp -4.43C Dewpoint -6.34C
From 11:05:00 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -5.32 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 56.32 deg (+ve N)

7000ft

6000ft CT

End P1

Start R1

R1 easing up to 5200

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 27 Feb 2009 1200 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 27 Feb 2009 1200 UTC

End R1 start P2

End P2 start R2

End R2 start P3

End P3 start R3

Into cloud -

End R3 start P4

End P4 start R4

Out of cloud

Into cloud again

Out again

In cloud again

Out of cloud again

In cloud again

Out for a while

Just over Oban - bumpy and now cloud

End R4 start P5

End P5 start R5

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 27 Feb 2009 1200 UTC

Just into CT - bumpy still turning

End R5 start P6

End P6 start R6

Cloud

Just under a completely sep lenticular

Flight B432 13:39:34
Heading 269 deg Speed 240 knots Height 8.0kft Press 752mb
Lat 56°24.0'N Long 4°18.0'W Wind 17 ms-1/242 deg
Temp -0.1C Dewpoint -4.9C
From 11:05:00 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -4.32 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 56.46 deg (+ve N)

End R6 start P7

End P7 start R7

End R7 start P8

End P8 start R8

End R8 start P9

End P9 start R9

Flight B432 14:19:42
Heading 262 deg Speed 240 knots Height 9.0kft Press 723mb
Lat 57°18.0'N Long 3°36.0'W Wind 18 ms-1/ 259 deg
Temp -3.25C Dewpoint -3.9C
From 11:05:00 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -3.63 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 57.3 deg (+ve N)

Flight B432 14:21:53
Heading 250 deg Speed 230 knots Height 9.0kft Press 723mb
Lat 57°12.0'N Long 3°48.0'W Wind 18 ms-1/ 251 deg
Temp -3.41C Dewpoint -3.51C
From 11:05:00 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -3.85 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 57.27 deg (+ve N)

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End R9 start P10

End P10 start R10

Flight Summary B432

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
Start-Up	09:51:09	308	0.17kft	52.1N	0.6W						52°04.36N, 0°37.48W
ASP	10:44:18	308	0.16kft	52.1N	0.6W						Open
T/O	11:05:45	308	0.74kft	52.1N	0.6W						Cranfield110447
Video	11:22:38	328	24.0kft	53.2N	1.7W						Start recording
Run t1	11:24:05	329	24.0kft	53.3N	1.8W	11:27:09	327	24.0kft	53.5N	2.0W	test comment
Profile 1	12:03:58	331	23.4kft	56.3N	4.2W	12:19:16	090	5.2kft	56.2N	5.6W	st120324
Run 1	12:19:33	077	5.3kft	56.2N	5.5W	12:19:34	077	5.3kft	56.2N	5.5W	Q1005
Run 1	12:20:19	076	5.2kft	56.2N	5.5W	12:32:02	071	5.5kft	56.4N	4.1W	
Profile 2	12:32:17	035	5.5kft	56.5N	4.0W	12:32:54	306	6.0kft	56.5N	4.0W	
Run 3	12:32:55	306	6.0kft	56.5N	4.0W	12:46:49	266	6.0kft	56.4N	5.4W	Run2!
Profile 3	12:47:04	243	6.0kft	56.4N	5.5W	12:47:49	143	6.5kft	56.3N	5.5W	coinc
Run 3	12:47:50	143	6.5kft	56.3N	5.5W	12:59:55	079	6.5kft	56.5N	4.0W	coinc
Profile 4	12:59:55	079	6.5kft	56.5N	4.0W	13:00:57	304	7.0kft	56.5N	3.9W	
Run 4	13:00:57	304	7.0kft	56.5N	3.9W	13:16:23	267	7.0kft	56.5N	5.5W	
Profile 5	13:16:24	264	7.0kft	56.5N	5.5W	13:17:37	102	7.5kft	56.4N	5.5W	
Run 5	13:17:37	102	7.5kft	56.4N	5.5W	13:31:16	077	7.5kft	56.5N	3.7W	
Event	13:23:37	093	7.5kft	56.5N	4.7W						Heimann cal
Profile 6	13:31:17	077	7.5kft	56.5N	3.7W	13:32:40	250	8.0kft	56.5N	3.7W	
Run 6	13:32:41	250	8.0kft	56.5N	3.7W	13:49:20	265	8.0kft	56.5N	5.4W	
Profile 7	13:49:21	265	8.0kft	56.5N	5.4W	13:50:03	183	8.5kft	56.4N	5.4W	
Run 7	13:50:03	183	8.5kft	56.4N	5.4W	14:02:30	089	8.5kft	56.4N	3.8W	
Profile 8	14:02:30	089	8.5kft	56.4N	3.8W	14:05:09	014	11.0kft	56.6N	2.7W	Belcaste

Cloud - a/c anti ice - CPI all water

R10 end P11

End P11 start R11

Out of cloud – turb probe iced up

Just over top of of lenticular cloud

End R11 start P12

End P13 start R13

A/c anti ice activated

End R13 start P14

End P14 start R14 - offset S for lenticular

End R14 start P15

Profile 4	12:59:55	079	6.5kft	56.5N	4.0W	13:00:57	304	7.0kft	56.5N	3.9W	
Run 4	13:00:57	304	7.0kft	56.5N	3.9W	13:16:23	267	7.0kft	56.5N	5.5W	
Profile 5	13:16:24	264	7.0kft	56.5N	5.5W	13:17:37	102	7.5kft	56.4N	5.5W	
Run 5	13:17:37	102	7.5kft	56.4N	5.5W	13:31:16	077	7.5kft	56.5N	3.7W	
Event	13:23:37	093	7.5kft	56.5N	4.7W						Heimann cal
Profile 6	13:31:17	077	7.5kft	56.5N	3.7W	13:32:40	250	8.0kft	56.5N	3.7W	
Run 6	13:32:41	250	8.0kft	56.5N	3.7W	13:49:20	265	8.0kft	56.5N	5.4W	
Profile 7	13:49:21	265	8.0kft	56.5N	5.4W	13:50:03	183	8.5kft	56.4N	5.4W	
Run 7	13:50:03	183	8.5kft	56.4N	5.4W	14:02:30	089	8.5kft	56.4N	3.8W	
Profile 8	14:02:30	089	8.5kft	56.4N	3.8W	14:05:08	014	11.0kft	56.6N	3.7W	Relocate
Run 8	14:05:08	014	11.0kft	56.6N	3.7W	14:14:46	014	11.0kft	57.3N	3.2W	Relocate
Profile 9	14:14:47	014	11.0kft	57.3N	3.2W	14:17:30	262	9.0kft	57.3N	3.4W	
Run 9	14:17:30	262	9.0kft	57.3N	3.4W	14:23:39	246	9.0kft	57.2N	4.0W	
Profile 10	14:23:39	246	9.0kft	57.2N	4.0W	14:25:19	071	10.5kft	57.2N	3.9W	
Run 10	14:25:20	071	10.5kft	57.2N	3.9W	14:32:30	091	10.5kft	57.2N	2.9W	
Profile 11	14:32:31	091	10.5kft	57.2N	2.9W	14:33:02	028	10.1kft	57.2N	2.8W	
Run 11	14:33:02	028	10.1kft	57.2N	2.8W	14:45:01	259	10.0kft	57.2N	4.0W	
Profile 12	14:45:01	259	10.0kft	57.2N	4.0W	14:46:03	122	9.5kft	57.2N	4.0W	
Run 12	14:46:03	122	9.5kft	57.2N	4.0W	14:53:57	089	9.5kft	57.2N	2.9W	
Profile 13	14:53:57	089	9.5kft	57.2N	2.9W	14:54:27	024	9.0kft	57.2N	2.9W	
Run 13	14:54:37	003	9.0kft	57.2N	2.9W	15:05:09	270	9.0kft	57.2N	3.9W	
Profile 14	15:05:10	270	9.0kft	57.2N	3.9W	15:06:25	108	9.5kft	57.2N	3.9W	Move south
Run 14	15:06:25	108	9.5kft	57.2N	3.9W	15:13:22	358	9.5kft	57.1N	3.0W	Move south
Profile 15	15:13:22	358	9.5kft	57.1N	3.0W						

End P15 R 15

End R15 start P16

End P16 start R16

Cloud tops

End R16 start P17

End P17 start R17

Well into cloud

Out of cloud now

End R17

Start R17.2

Into Cloud Tops

Out of cloud

Into CT

Out of cloud

In cloud

Out of cloud

End of R17.2

Run 1 eastbound at MSA

Run 2 westbound

Run 3 eastbound

Run 4 westbound

Run 5 eastbound

Run 6 westbound

Run 7 eastbound

Run 8 northeast-bound

Run 9 westbound in NE

Run 10 eastbound in NE

Run 11 westbound in NE

Run 12 eastbound in NE

Run 13 westbound in NE

Run 14 eastbound in NE

Recovering to Prestwick

Profile 7	13:49:21	265	8.0kft	56.5N	5.4W	13:50:03	183	8.5kft	56.4N	5.4W	
Run 7	13:50:03	183	8.5kft	56.4N	5.4W	14:02:30	089	8.5kft	56.4N	3.8W	
Profile 8	14:02:30	089	8.5kft	56.4N	3.8W	14:05:08	014	11.0kft	56.6N	3.7W	Relocate
Run 8	14:05:08	014	11.0kft	56.6N	3.7W	14:14:46	014	11.0kft	57.3N	3.2W	Relocate
Profile 9	14:14:47	014	11.0kft	57.3N	3.2W	14:17:30	262	9.0kft	57.3N	3.4W	
Run 9	14:17:30	262	9.0kft	57.3N	3.4W	14:23:39	246	9.0kft	57.2N	4.0W	
Profile 10	14:23:39	246	9.0kft	57.2N	4.0W	14:25:19	071	10.5kft	57.2N	3.9W	
Run 10	14:25:20	071	10.5kft	57.2N	3.9W	14:32:30	091	10.5kft	57.2N	2.9W	
Profile 11	14:32:31	091	10.5kft	57.2N	2.9W	14:33:02	028	10.1kft	57.2N	2.8W	
Run 11	14:33:02	028	10.1kft	57.2N	2.8W	14:45:01	259	10.0kft	57.2N	4.0W	
Profile 12	14:45:01	259	10.0kft	57.2N	4.0W	14:46:03	122	9.5kft	57.2N	4.0W	
Run 12	14:46:03	122	9.5kft	57.2N	4.0W	14:53:57	089	9.5kft	57.2N	2.9W	
Profile 13	14:53:57	089	9.5kft	57.2N	2.9W	14:54:27	024	9.0kft	57.2N	2.9W	
Run 13	14:54:37	003	9.0kft	57.2N	2.9W	15:05:09	270	9.0kft	57.2N	3.9W	
Profile 14	15:05:10	270	9.0kft	57.2N	3.9W	15:06:25	108	9.5kft	57.2N	3.9W	Move south
Run 14	15:06:25	108	9.5kft	57.2N	3.9W	15:13:22	358	9.5kft	57.1N	3.0W	Move south
Profile 15	15:13:22	358	9.5kft	57.1N	3.0W	15:16:26	281	8.0kft	57.1N	3.3W	
Run 15	15:16:27	281	8.0kft	57.1N	3.3W	15:18:45	254	7.0kft	57.1N	3.5W	
Event	15:17:08	271	8.0kft	57.1N	3.3W						Zero nevz
Run 16	15:19:06	258	7.0kft	57.1N	3.5W	15:25:30	267	7.0kft	57.1N	4.2W	to 6k',Q1001
Profile 17	15:25:30	267	7.0kft	57.1N	4.2W	15:26:48	092	6.3kft	57.1N	4.2W	to 6k',Q1001
Run 17	15:26:48	092	6.3kft	57.1N	4.2W	15:34:57	092	6.4kft	57.1N	3.2W	
Run 17.2	15:38:04	271	6.4kft	57.1N	3.3W	15:46:08	271	6.4kft	57.1N	4.1W	6k'
Transit	15:49:03	201	12.6kft	57.0N	4.3W						To Prestwick

Recovering to Prestwick